

Perceptions And Readiness Of Undergraduate Educational Technology Students Towards The Use Of Nearpod Instructional Platform For Enhancing Academic Achievement In Sokoto State University, Nigeria

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The research entitled “perceptions and readiness of undergraduate educational technology students towards the use of Nearpod instructional platform for enhancing academic achievement in Sokoto State University” was guided by two objectives and two research questions. A descriptive survey research design was employed and the population comprised 1,544 undergraduate students enrolled in the Faculty of Education during 2023/2024 academic session. A sample of 154 students was selected using multi-stage sampling of stratified and simple random sampling methods. Data were collected with a structured questionnaire. The research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically mean and percentage.

The findings revealed that students perceived Nearpod educational platform as highly beneficial in improving their academic achievement. Respondents also demonstrated strong readiness to adopt the platform, showing confidence in their ability to adapt to new technologies and a willingness to dedicate time to use it for learning purposes. Furthermore, the results indicated that Nearpod instructional platform fostered collaboration between students and academic staff, as well as among peers, thereby enhancing interaction and participation in the learning process. The findings recommended the adoption of Nearpod instructional platform for enhancing the quality of teaching and learning, making it a valuable tool for advancing academic achievement and improving instructional practices.

Keywords:
Perception,
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Nearpod
platform.

Introduction

Integration of technology into education has become a fundamental foundation of contemporary teaching and learning, shifting conventional educational presentations and enhancing student engagement. Among many technological tools, Nearpod, a cloud-based instructional platform, has gained significant attention for its possibilities in improving academic achievement. Nearpod

platform allows instructors to create interactive lessons that incorporate multimedia elements, quizzes, polls, and collaborative activities, all designed to promote student participation and active learning. The platform was found to be effective in engaging students, providing real-time feedback, and fostering a more dynamic learning environment (Graham et

al., 2017; Saeed & Zyngier, 2012) across different part of the world in general and some part of the Nigeria.

Nigerian universities, including Sokoto State University, the adoption of educational technologies has been recognized as essential for improving the quality of higher education (Awofala et al., 2020). However, the extent to which students, especially those in Educational Technology (ET) programs, are prepared to embrace these tools remains unclear. Educational Technology students are often expected to be early adopters of digital learning platforms due to their focus on technology integration in education. Thus, understanding their perceptions and readiness to use platforms like Nearpod instructional platform is crucial for the successful implementation of such tools in teaching and learning. Theoretical framework guiding this study was drawn on established models of technology adoption, particularly the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989), the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003), and Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers, 2003). According to TAM, users' acceptance of technology is primarily determined by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, which directly influence their attitudes toward using digital platforms. UTAUT extends this by emphasizing factors such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions, all of which shape technology adoption in educational settings. Diffusion of Innovations Theory further explained how innovations like Nearpod instructional platform are adopted over time, stressing the importance of relative advantage,

compatibility, complexity, trainability, and observability in determining adoption rates and perception.

Perception and readiness are critical determinants of technology adoption in the teaching and learning process. Previous research has shown that students' perceptions of technology significantly influence their willingness to use digital tools for learning (Teo, 2011). In particular, ease of use, perceived usefulness, and self-efficacy play crucial roles in shaping attitudes toward technology integration (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). Additionally, readiness to adopt new technologies is often affected by students' digital literacy levels, access to resources, and prior experience with similar platforms (Liu et al., 2014). These theoretical perspectives collectively provide a lens for understanding how Educational Technology students in Sokoto State University may perceive and respond to the use of Nearpod instructional platform.

Sokoto State University, where technological resources are being gradually integrated into the academic background, understanding the readiness and perceptions of Educational Technology students toward the Nearpod instructional platform will provide valuable insights into how best to enhance academic experiences through technology. It is essential to determine whether these students, who are expected to lead future educational technology initiatives, are prepared to use Nearpod instructional platform to its full utilization and whether they perceive it as a valuable tool for enhancing academic achievement. Guided by TAM, UTAUT, and Diffusion of Innovations Theory, this study investigated their perceptions and readiness, with the goal of providing recommendations for improving the use of Nearpod and similar platforms

within the university, to foster digital literacy and technology integration in Nigerian higher education.

Statement of the Problem

The role of educational technology in enhancing teaching and learning has gained important attention globally, with various digital platforms showing benefits in improving student engagement, knowledge retention, and overall academic achievement. Among these, Nearpod, a cloud-based instructional tool, has emerged as a powerful platform capable of facilitating interactive lessons, formative assessments, and real-time feedback. Nearpod's ability to incorporate multimedia resources, polls, quizzes, and collaborative activities offers a dynamic and engaging learning experience that has the potential to significantly enhance academic achievement (Graham et al., 2017; Saeed & Zyngier, 2012; Muhammad et al., 2023). However, despite the proven effectiveness of Nearpod in various educational settings, the readiness and perceptions towards this platform, particularly in Sokoto State University, remain largely under explored by using educational technology students.

Educational Technology students, who are expected to be familiar with current digital tools and their applications in learning environments, may not necessarily be ready to embrace new technologies such as Nearpod. This lack of readiness could stem from a variety of factors, including insufficient digital literacy, lack of access to adequate technological resources, and resistance to adopting unfamiliar platforms (Awofala et al., 2020). Moreover, the perceptions of these students regarding the effectiveness and utility of Nearpod for academic achievement play a crucial role in their willingness to adopt the platform.

Understanding how these students perceive Nearpod, along with their readiness to integrate it into their learning processes, is essential for facilitating the successful use of the platform and maximizing its role in enhancing learning outcomes.

Learning outcomes are clear statements of expected knowledge, skills, abilities. Although prior studies have examined technology adoption in education (Teo, 2011; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000), several shortcomings remain. Firstly, most existing research has been conducted in technologically advanced perspectives, with limited focus on developing countries where infrastructural challenges, intermittent internet access, and limited institutional support constrain adoption. Additionally, the majority of Nearpod-related studies emphasize general student populations or specific subject areas (e.g., science or language learning) without considering students enrolled in Educational Technology programs, which are uniquely positioned as future technology facilitators. Moreover, many studies rely heavily on self-reported surveys, which capture perceptions but often fail to critically examine actual readiness, resource availability, and long-term adoption behaviors. Furthermore, within the Nigerian setting, few studies have critically engaged with the intersection of students' digital literacy, cultural factors, and institutional barriers, leaving a gap in understanding how these related variables influence technology adoption. Concisely, there is a gap in research concerning the perceptions and readiness of undergraduate educational technology students in Sokoto State University towards Nearpod educational platform, a gap that this study seeks to address. Therefore, this study investigated the perceptions and readiness of undergraduate educational technology

students in Sokoto State University towards using Nearpod educational platform as a tool for enhancing academic achievement.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of the study was to investigate the perceptions and readiness of undergraduate educational technology students towards use of Nearpod instructional platform for enhancing academic achievement in Sokoto state university. Specifically, the objectives are:

1. To determine the perceptions of undergraduate educational technology students towards the Nearpod instructional platform for enhancing academic achievement in Sokoto State University.
2. To evaluate the readiness of undergraduate educational technology students in adopting the Nearpod instructional platform for learning at Sokoto State University.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised and answered in the study:

1. What are the perceptions of undergraduate educational technology students in Sokoto State University towards the Nearpod instructional platform for enhancing academic achievement?

2. What is the level of readiness of undergraduate educational technology students in adopting the Nearpod instructional platform for learning in Sokoto State University?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed descriptive survey design, it is a research approach used to systematically collect data on individuals' attitudes, opinions or behaviors without manipulating variables. In the investigation of undergraduate educational technology students' perceptions and readiness toward the Nearpod platform, this design helps captured views on the platform's usefulness, effectiveness, and their preparedness to adopt it for enhancing academic achievement. Surveys can be administered through structured questionnaires or interviews, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative measures to evaluate readiness and perceptions (Creswell, 2017).

The population of the study consisted of all the undergraduate students enrolled in the faculty of education in Sokoto State University that offered courses leading to B.Sc./B.A.Ed. degree programme in the 2023/2024 academic session. The targeted population was 1,544 (300 level) undergraduate students from the university and it is illustrated in table 1 below.

Table 1: Distribution of undergraduate students' target population across the departments in the faculty of Education, Sokoto State University

S/N	Department	Undergraduate Students Population
1.	Curriculum Studies	364
2.	Education Management	306
3.	Education Science	471
4.	Guidance and Counseling	403
	Total	1544

Source: (Faculty Officer, 2024)

Sampling Techniques and Sample

A multi-stage sampling of stratified and simple random sampling methods was used for selection of sample from the population that was adequately a representative of the population. The rationale for choosing of these methods were due to the fact that the

Undergraduate students in the departments were not equally populated and in line with Ibanga (2002) recommendation on sample for descriptive survey study to consisted of 10–20% of the population, hence each departments contributed the sample according to it is size.

Table 2: Sample for the Study

S/N	Department	Undergraduate Students Sample
1.	Curriculum Studies	36
2.	Education Management	31
3.	Education Science	47
4.	Guidance and Counseling	40
Total		154

Source: Researcher's field work, 2025.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection in the study was a self-constructed questionnaire titled Undergraduate Students' Perception and Readiness toward Nearpod educational platform for Enhancing Academic Achievement (UPRNAA). It was developed specifically to measure the two central constructs of the study: students' perceptions and their readiness to use Nearpod in learning. The development of the questionnaire followed a systematic process to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the research questions.

The items were generated through a comprehensive review of related literature and theories of technology adoption. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) and Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003) guided the formulation of perception-related items, particularly focusing on perceived usefulness and ease of use. Similarly, literature on digital readiness and adoption (Teo, 2011;

Liu et al., 2014) informed the readiness-related items, emphasizing digital literacy, access to resources, and confidence in using educational technology.

The instrument consisted of two sections namely Section A and B.

Section A: Perceptions (4 items) – These items assessed students' views on the usefulness, interactivity, and effectiveness of Nearpod for enhancing academic achievement. Section B: Readiness (4 items): These items measured students' preparedness in terms of skills, resources, and willingness to adopt Nearpod in their learning. Responses were captured using a 4-point Likert's scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). The scaling format was chosen to avoid a neutral midpoint and encourage respondents to take a clear position.

Validity of the Instruments

The face and content validity of the instrument (UPRNAA) was determined by giving it to experts in the Department of Psychology, Guidance and Counseling,

Faculty of Education, Sokoto State University, Sokoto State, Nigeria, for judgment. These experts were provided with copies of the instrument, the study topic, aim and objectives, as well as the research questions. They carefully reviewed the instrument for clarity, appropriateness of items, relevance to the study objectives, and alignment with the research questions. Based on their recommendations, ambiguous items were reworded for better clarity, overlapping statements were either merged or removed, and some items were added to cover overlooked aspects of perception and readiness. The structure, sequencing, and wording of the questionnaire were also refined to ensure ease of understanding by respondents. Their constructive comments and suggestions were strictly incorporated in the final development of the instrument to enhance its validity and suitability for the study.

Reliability of the Instrument

The measure of internal consistency of the UPRNAA was determined by administering it to 30 respondents (10 academic staff and 20 students) in the Faculty of Science, Sokoto State University, Sokoto. The Faculty of Science was selected because the respondents possess similar characteristics with the actual study sample, thereby providing a reliable basis for the trial

testing. The internal consistency was measured using the split-half method, and the reliability coefficient was computed using the Kuder–Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20), which yielded a coefficient of 0.78. The KR-20 was chosen because the instrument items were structured on a dichotomous response format (Agree/Disagree type choices), and KR-20 is most appropriate for estimating reliability in such cases. This approach ensures that the reliability reflects the degree to which the items consistently measure the same construct across different subsets of the test.

RESULT AND DISCUSION

The data collected was analyzed by the use of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24:0; Data was analyzed based on research questions. in which, research questions were answered by descriptive statistics of percentage and mean through using the 50% and mean criterion of 2.5 obtained from four points likert scale as criteria for accepting or otherwise i.e. $4+3+2+1/4 = 2.5$.

Research Question One

What are the perceptions of undergraduate educational technology students at Sokoto State University towards the Nearpod platform for enhancing academic achievement?

Table 3: Perception of Undergraduate students toward Nearpod Platform for enhancing academic achievement.

S/N	Items	Percentage responses			Mean (x)	
		Strongly agree (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly disagree (%)		
1	I believe that using the Nearpod Platform will make learning more interactive.	46.3	20.4	14.9	18.4	2.95
2	Nearpod platform has the potential to improve my academic achievement.	44.1	21.6	11.9	22.4	2.88
3	I think Nearpod Platform will make learning more engaging compared to face-to-face learning	53.1	22.1	16.4	8.1	3.18
4	Nearpod Platform’s collaborative features, such as group activities and live poll will enhance my academic achievement	24.9	26.1	13.5	35.5	2.40
5	I believe Nearpod Platform is user-friendly and easy to navigate.	56.4	17.5	21.5	4.6	3.24
6	I believe using Nearpod Platform will encourage active participation.	57.3	18.8	12.7	11.2	3.22
7	I feel Nearpod Platform can improve communication between students and lectures.	38.8	23.4	9.3	28.5	2.72
8	The content delivered through Nearpod Platform will be more interesting than in regular lectures.	42.2	13.4	5.7	38.7	2.58

Table 3 indicated that respondent who believe that using the Nearpod Platform will make learning more interactive, choose Strongly Agree, Agree and mean of 46.3%, 20.4% and 2.95 respectively. Similarly 44.1%, 21.6% and 2.88 of the respondents indicated that the Nearpod platform has the potential to improve their academic

achievement with strongly agree, agree and mean score respectively. The data further revealed that Nearpod Platform will make learning more engaging compared to face-to-face learning; Nearpod Platform’s collaborative features, such as group activities and live poll, will enhance student academic achievement, Nearpod Platform is

user-friendly and easy to navigate using Nearpod Platform will encourage active participation; I feel Nearpod Platform can improve communication between students and lectures and the content delivered through Nearpod Platform will be more interesting than in regular lectures, were

strongly agree and agree. More so, 50 % and almost the mean scores of the respondents perceived Nearpod platform as strong learning tool for improved academic achievement.

S/n	Items	Percentage responses			Mean	
		Strongly agree	Agree	Strongly disagree		
1	I am comfortable using technology (e.g Nearpod Platform) for learning purposes.	39.4	17.8	5.2	37.6	2.59
2	I am willing to learn how to use the Nearpod platform for academic activities.	47.4	34.2	16.7	1.7	3.27
3	I am ready to dedicate time to familiarize myself with the features of the Nearpod Platform.	44.2	38.5	1.6	15.7	3.11
4	I am willing to participate in training sessions to effectively use Nearpod Platform.	34.1	17.9	42.4	5.6	2.81
5	I have access to the necessary technology (such as smart phone, tablet, or computer) to use the Nearpod Platform.	19.1	44.8	8.3	27.8	2.55
6	I have reliable internet access to use the Nearpod Platform effectively.	31.5	20.3	46.2	2.0	2.81
7	I believe the cost of using the Nearpod Platform such as, internet charges will not be a barrier for me.	27.2	42.3	22.1	8.4	2.88
8	I am confident in my ability to adapt to new technologies like Nearpod Platform.	40.1	15.0	3.8	15.0	2.28

Table 4: Undergraduate students Readiness for using the Nearpod Platform in enhancing academic achievement.

Result in table 4 shows that 39.4% and 17.8% of the sample respondents indicated that they

are comfortable using technology (e.g Smartphones, tablet, or computers) for

learning purposes with strongly agreed, agreed and a mean of 2.59; 47.4% and 34.2% had strongly agreed and agreed of I am willing to learn how to use the Nearpod platform for academic activities which was above the 50% bench mark. Moreover, I am ready to dedicate time to familiarize myself with the features of the Nearpod Platform, I am willing to participate in training sessions to effectively use Nearpod Platform, I have access to the necessary technology (such as smart phone, tablet, or computer) to use the Nearpod Platform and I have reliable internet access to use the Nearpod Platform effectively responded to strongly agree, agree and with high mean score. Furthermore, the data revealed that I believe the cost of using the Nearpod Platform such as internet charges will not be a barrier for me, and I am confident in my ability to adapt to new technologies like Nearpod Platform had agreed as their readiness to use Nearpod platform for learning educational technology.

Discussion of Findings

From the analyzed data, the findings indicated that the Nearpod platform has strong impending to improve students' academic achievement by making learning more interactive and engaging compared to conventional face-to-face instruction. This result anchored with the submission of Graham et al. (2017), who emphasized that Nearpod's ability to integrate multimedia resources, polls, quizzes, and collaborative activities provides a dynamic and stimulating learning environment that can significantly enhance students' performance. Similarly, Muhammad et al. (2023) also reported that students exposed to Nearpod and other remote learning technologies demonstrated improved academic achievement, underscoring the tool's relevance in

contemporary higher education. The consistency of these findings across different settings suggests that Nearpod's interactive features contribute positively to learning outcomes by fostering engagement, immediate feedback, and active participation, all of which are critical elements in constructivist learning environments.

Furthermore, the second major result revealed that students were generally comfortable with using technology for academic purposes. They expressed readiness to invest time in familiarizing themselves with the Nearpod platform and did not consider associated costs, such as internet charges, to be major barriers. In a nutshell, they demonstrated confidence in their ability to adapt to emerging technologies. This finding confirms Galadima et al. (2019) observation that students' confidence in adapting to innovative platforms enhances their willingness to adopt new technologies for learning. The result was further supported by Hassan et al. (2020) as well as Aliyu et al. (2023), who found that positive attitudes and readiness to adopt educational technology strongly predict successful integration into academic settings. The convergence of these findings indicates that students' technological readiness and adaptability are crucial determinants of the effective adoption of Nearpod in higher education.

Nevertheless, while the present study linked with previous literature, minor discrepancies can be observed. For instance, some studies highlighted that in low-resource settings, infrastructural and internet connectivity challenges are barriers to technology adoption (Hassan et al., 2020), whereas respondents in this study reported that internet costs would not constitute a significant barrier. This divergence may be

attributed to institutional support structures, such as subsidized internet access or students' increasing familiarity with mobile data usage, which could mitigate concerns about connectivity. Another significant reason was the growing digital literacy among Nigerian undergraduates, which has improved over the past decade and may reduce resistance to adopting platforms like Nearpod.

Briefly, these findings suggest that Nearpod educational platform, when properly implemented, has chances not only to improve academic achievement and retention but also to address broader educational concerns, such as narrowing the digital divide and bridging gender gaps in teaching and learning. The alignment with prior studies reinforces the reliability of the results, while the noted discrepancies highlighted the importance of some factors like infrastructure, institutional support, and student digital literacy in shaping technology adoption outcomes

Conclusion

The findings of this study contained several important implications for the implementation of Nearpod and similar educational technology platforms. First, the students' overwhelming confidence and readiness to adapt to Nearpod suggest that higher education institutions can capitalize on this positive disposition by integrating Nearpod more systematically into course delivery. This can be achieved by embedding interactive features such as quizzes, polls, and collaborative boards into lecture sessions to enhance engagement and deepen understanding. Educators should be trained not only in the technical use of Nearpod but also in pedagogical strategies for designing interactive, student-centered lessons that leverage the platform's full potential.

Moreover, the positive perception of online learning experiences indicates that Nearpod can serve as a bridge between face-to-face and online learning, particularly in blended or hybrid learning models. This flexibility is particularly relevant in settings where infrastructure challenges may prevent full-scale online Adoption. Used of Nearpod educational platforms in physical classrooms as well as in remote learning environments, institutions can create a seamless and engaging learning experience that transcends location barriers.

Additionally, the finding that internet cost and access were not perceived as significant barriers is noteworthy for Nigerian and other developing country, where connectivity is often a challenge. This suggested that with proper institutional support such as subsidized data bundles, provision of Wi-Fi hotspots, or zero-rated educational platforms—students are likely to engage meaningfully with online learning tools. Policymakers and administrators should therefore prioritize supportive infrastructure and policies to sustain this readiness.

Finally, the confidence students expressed in adapting to new technologies showed the importance of continuous exposure to innovative platforms. Integrating Nearpod educational platform early in teacher training programs, for example, could cultivate a new generation of educators who are both digitally literate and pedagogically skilled in utilizing technology for learning, which in turn enhance instructional quality, boost academic achievement, and prepare students for a digital economy.

Suggestions for further studies

The findings were encouraging and they also open avenues for further studies.

1. Future studies should examine the long-term impact of Nearpod adoption on learning outcomes across multiple courses

and faculties, as this study was limited to a single institution. Such cross-disciplinary research would help determine whether the positive effects observed are consistent across diverse learning environments.

2. There is a need for comparative research between Nearpod and other interactive platforms (e.g., Kahoot, ClassDojo, or Google Classroom) to identify the relative advantages and limitations of each in improving academic achievement. This would provide educators and policymakers with evidence-based guidance for selecting the most suitable platforms for their settings.
3. Future research should determine the role of related variables such as gender, socio-economic status, and digital literacy in shaping students' readiness and adaptability to platforms like Nearpod. Understanding these could inform more targeted interventions to bridge gaps in technology adoption and ensure inclusivity.
4. Given that the current findings suggest minimal concern about internet costs, it would be useful to investigate the sustainability of this perception over time. For example, longitudinal studies could assess whether students continue to view connectivity as non-restrictive when Nearpod is integrated at scale across different institutions with varying levels of support.
5. Research should also examine the perspectives of lecturers and administrators regarding the adoption of Nearpod. While student readiness is critical, the effective implementation of educational technology depends equally on instructors' willingness, competence, and institutional policies. A multi-stakeholder approach to future studies would therefore provide a more holistic understanding of the opportunities and challenges of Nearpod adoption.

Limitations of the Study

Considering the valuable insights generated from this study, certain limitations must be acknowledged.

1. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which relied solely on self-reported data collected through structured questionnaires. Such responses may be influenced by social desirability bias or personal interpretation of the items, thereby affecting the accuracy of the findings.
2. The sample size of 154 undergraduate students, though scientifically selected through stratified and simple random sampling, represents only a small fraction of the total population of 1,544 students in the Faculty of Education. This limited representation may constrain the generalizability of the results to the wider undergraduate population, particularly across other faculties or institutions with different academic and technological backgrounds.
3. The scope of the study was restricted to Sokoto State University within the 2023/2024 academic session. As such, the findings may not fully reflect perceptions and readiness toward the Nearpod instructional platform in other universities or over a longer timeframe, where differences in infrastructure, institutional policies, and exposure to technology could yield varying outcomes.

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